

Date: <date>

Participant: <name>

Startup: <type>

Duration: max. 1 hour

Objective

This is a research, development, and innovation project that aims to investigate how User eXperience (UX) work has been carried out in software startups. We refer to software startups as emerging companies whose main goal is to develop innovative software-intensive products, constantly seeking a repeatable and scalable business model.

In our initial investigation, we identified some issues that are relevant to implementing UX activities and practices in startups. In this stage of the investigation, we intend to understand how widely these issues are frequently identified by startups.

We invite you to this interview, which is open to professionals working in software startups, including software engineers, testers, UX designers, project managers, product managers, software architects, among others. To participate, there are no restrictions on the size of the startup in which the professional works.

Thank you for your participation!

Consent Statement

We will listen to you and take some notes, however, we would like to record this interview. The recording will only be used for research purposes by the people involved in the project, and will not be disclosed in any way, not even your data. Therefore, I would like to know if you allow the recording of our conversation.

If you do, I will start the recording and ask for your consent again, so that it is documented (confirm that the TCLE - Free and Informed Consent Form has been signed)

1- Demographic questions

- *What is your age?*
- *What is the highest degree or educational level you have completed?*
- *Which professional profiles best reflect your current work at the startup you work for?*
- *How many years of practical experience do you have in your field?*
- *How long have you been working at the startup?*
- *Where is the startup you work for located? (city/state)*
- *When was the startup founded? Please provide the year (e.g.: 2021)*
- *Briefly describe the product(s)/service(s) developed at the startup.*
- *How many employees does the startup have?*
- *How many people work in software development?*
- *How many customers/users does the startup have?*
- *What is the classification of the startup's business model?*
- *What is the most important industry that the startup serves or develops software for?*
- *Considering the main product/service developed at the startup, indicate its current status.*

- *Does the startup you work for have specific UX positions? By positions, consider the professionals who work with UX methodologies, techniques or practices.*
- *Does the startup you work for use UX methodologies, techniques or practices in the development of products/services?*
- *How many years ago were UX methodologies, techniques or practices introduced in the startup?*

2- Introduce the interview dynamics:

For participants who answered the survey:

Part 1 - Briefly describe the activities you do at the startup

Part 2 - Give us more detail about the questions you answered in the survey

Part 3 - Please, assess the presence of other issues

- *For each statement¹* that we will present inform:*
 - *Do you recognize this problem in the startup you work for?*
 - *a problem that does not yet have a solution.*
 - *a problem that is being solved.*
 - *a problem that existed but has already been solved.*
 - *a problem that has not yet been identified in the startup.*
 - *Please tell us a little more, for example, how it was solved or more details about the problem in your startup.*

For participants who had not answered the survey:

Part 1 - Briefly describe the activities you do in the startup

Part 2 - Answer to what extent some issues that we identified in other startups are also related to the startup you work for.

- *For each statement¹ that we will present inform:*
 - *Do you recognize this problem in the startup you work for?*
 - *a problem that does not yet have a solution.*
 - *a problem that is being solved.*
 - *a problem that existed but has already been solved.*
 - *a problem that has not yet been identified in the startup.*
 - *Please tell us a little more, for example, how it was solved or more details about the problem in your startup.*

¹ The statements are the same as those made in the survey